

Guidelines

1. METHODS OF SUBMISSION AND EVALUATION OF WORKS

Researchers interested in publishing their work in Ediciones Clío should send their proposal to the following emails. esdicionesclio.es@gmail.com.

Proposals must have: identification of the author or authors, indicating: name, surname, institution that they represent (university, institute, research center, foundation), email, curriculum summary of each author with an extension no greater than ten (10) lines, incorporate the link of each ORCID of each author and provide a cell phone number with the international code of the country of origin. Likewise, a written communication signed by the authors and addressed to the director of the magazine will be presented stating that he expresses interest in proposing their work for publication.

Proposed articles or writings must be unpublished and must not have been simultaneously proposed to other publications. All works will be evaluated by a Committee of Specialist Referees of recognized prestige in each of the areas of knowledge that are proposed. The evaluation of the Referees will be carried out through the procedure known as a pair of blind men: the referees and the authors will not know their respective identities. The evaluation criteria are the following:

a.- Formal or presentation criteria: 1) originality, relevance and adequate extension of the title; 2) clarity and coherence of speech; 3) adequate preparation of the summary; 4) internal organization of the text; 5) all other criteria established in these regulations.

b.- Content criteria: 1) domain of evidenced knowledge; 2) scientific rigor; 3) theoretical and methodological foundation; 4) topicality and relevance of the sources consulted; 5) contributions to existing knowledge.

Upon receipt of the response from the appointed Referees Committee, the authors will be informed by email of the corresponding decision; In case of being accepted, the work should be sent by email to the contacts - mail, WhatsApp - provided by the magazine.

2. PRESENTATION OF THE WORKS

The works must present an abstract of 150 words maximum and up to four keywords; both the abstract and the keywords will be in Spanish and English. Likewise, the title and subtitle of the work will also be presented in Spanish and English. The maximum length of the work must not exceed a maximum of twenty (20) pages and a minimum of fifteen (15). All papers will be presented in letter-size digital Word format, with continuous numbering and with margins of (2) centimeters on each side. The text will be presented at a space and a half, in Times New Roman font, size 12. For footnotes, the size will be in Times New Roman font size 10.

3. BODY OF THE ARTICLE

Title: It should be short, explanatory and contain the essence of the work. This title must be provided in both Spanish and English.

Author (s): Indicate the full names and surnames, the name of the institution where the work was carried out or the institution to which the author belongs. This should be placed as a footnote on the first page of the article.

Abstract: No more than one hundred fifty (150) words, in Spanish and English. In case the work is presented in another language. The abstract must be written in the same language, in Spanish and English.

Keywords: Keywords in Spanish and English should be included in a number that ranges from three to four words. These descriptive words facilitate the inclusion of the article in the international database.

Sections and Sub-sections: It is recommended, if applicable, to divide the work into: summary, introduction, theoretical foundations, methodology, analysis or discussion, conclusion or final considerations and references. Each of the sections or sub-sections will be numbered with Arabic numerals.

Citations: The citation will be made in the text using the author-date modality, indicating, if it is a textual appointment, it is located within the parentheses: last name (s) of the author, comma, year of publication of the work, followed by a colon and the number (s) of the page (s), for example: according to (Granadillo, 1998: 45); if it is not a textual quotation but a paraphrase, the year number will not be indicated, for example: according to Granadillo (1998) or (Granadillo, 1998). If there are several works by the same author published in the same year, they will be arranged literally in alphabetical order; for example, (Granadillo, 2008a: 12), Granadillo (2008b:

24). If there are two authors, only the first surname of each will be placed, for example: According to Pietri and Granadillo (2008: 90) or (Pietri and Granadillo, 2008: 90), following the same criteria explained above for textual citations and paraphrase. If there are three or more authors, the last name of the main author will be placed followed by "et al", example: (Rincón et al, 2008: 45). Quotations from unpublished works or works in print, as well as references to communications and private documents of limited circulation, should be avoided as much as possible, unless strictly necessary. In the case of documentary, electronic or other sources that by their nature are unviable or complex for the adoption of the aforementioned author - date, suggested in these regulations, the one cited at the bottom of the page can be resorted to or chosen.

Bibliographic references: References (bibliographic, newspaper, oral and / or documentary) will be presented at the end of the text. The order of the references is alphabetical by surname. The different works by the same author will be organized chronologically, in ascending order, and if there are two or more works by the same author and year, the strict alphabetical order by title will be maintained.

They will refer only to those cited in the work and will be ordered in strict alphabetical order. Authors are responsible for the accuracy of the references.

If they are books or manuals, they must contain surname (s) and name (s), of the authors in capital letters (period); year of publication in parentheses (period) title of work in bold (period), place of editorial publication.

If it is information obtained by electronic means, the bibliographic reference must contain the same elements indicated by the articles added to: electronic means, address electronic or web page, date of retrieval and any other information that is considered useful for the full identification of the reference.

Annexes: the annexes constitute complementary elements of the text that the reader refers to a part of the work or outside of it, with the purpose of illustrating the ideas presented in the text, expanding or clarifying or complementing what is expressed there. The annexes are counted as part of the number of pages of the document. In the case of figures and tables, the author may accompany the original with the illustrations that he deems necessary.

Other Works: The following short works are also accepted (maximum fifteen pages): Conferences, Essays, Reviews: recent reading comments. Reviews: critical analysis (or comment) of recent reading, documents, texts of a historical and legal nature, agreements, statements, interviews: carried out for research purposes.

Any other unforeseen situation will be resolved by the editors as they deem appropriate to the interests of the magazine.

4. OBJECTIVES AND SCOPE OF THE PUBLICATION.

Focus and scope

The Clío magazine is a publication sponsored by Ediciones Clío, the Academy of History of the Zulia State, the Zulia Center for Genealogical Research, the Center for Historical Studies of the University of Zulia and the International Network on Research Teaching; among other associated centers.

Its objectives include:

- Contribute to the scientific progress of Historical Science and Human Sciences, through the dissemination of research and research advances proposed by their authors.
- Stimulate research in Social Sciences, as well as in all related disciplines.
- Promote the presentation, discussion and confrontation of ideas and scientific advances with social commitment.

Clío appears at least twice a year and publishes original works with advances or research results in the areas of Sciences described above, which are submitted to the consideration of qualified referees.

5. PRIVACY STATEMENT

Clío magazine publicly recognizes the ethical commitment of all parties involved in the process of intellectual development of research or research advances. In accordance with the provisions of current Data Protection regulations, we inform you that the person responsible for data treatment is personal. It will only be used to answer questions and any type of management carried out by this means of communication, reason for which, your data will not be transferred to third parties, except by legal obligation.

You have the right to access, rectify or delete erroneous data, request the limitation of the processing of your data as well as oppose or withdraw consent at any time.

6. STAGES OF THE EDITORIAL PROCESS

Once the Editor and the Editorial Committee receive an article, the review will begin in seven weeks, plus three weeks for its publication, which are subject to the periodicity of Clío. Journal of History, Human Sciences and Critical Thought.

Stage 1: Internal review or pre-review, within a period of two (2) weeks. The correspondence between citations and references, the thematic compatibility of the article with the disciplinary blocks of the journal, as well as the control and verification of plagiarism through software on the Web will be verified. The author will be informed about the acceptance or rejection to continue in the arbitration process.

Stage 2: External review, within a period of four (4) weeks, through the inclusion of two specialist pairs, as reviewers of the article under the double-blind modality, and in case of disagreement in the evaluation, a third evaluator will be assigned to settle disagreements. These specialists will make observations and issue a concept in terms of: (a) Publishable without modifications, (b) Publishable with slight modifications, (c) Publishable with substantial modifications, (d) Not publishable. As can be seen in our evaluation instrument.

The following criteria are taken into account in the arbitration process:

a. Content criteria: a) domain of evidenced knowledge; b) scientific rigor; c) theoretical and methodological foundation; d) topicality and relevance of the sources consulted; f) contributions to existing knowledge.

b. Formal or presentation criteria: 1) originality, relevance and adequate extension of the title; 2) clarity and coherence of speech; 3) adequate preparation of the summary; 4) internal organization of the text.

The format used by reviewers to evaluate articles includes two main parameters: formal or presentation criteria and content criteria, which will be evaluated on a scale that expresses the values: E = Excellent B = Good R = Fair D = Poor

Formal or presentation criteria: 1) Originality, relevance and adequate extension of the title; 2) Clarity and coherence of speech; 3) Adequate preparation of the summary: objective, methodology, results and keywords; 4) internal organization of the text.

Content criteria: 1) Domain of evidenced knowledge; 2) Scientific rigor; 3) Theoretical and methodological foundation; 4) Actuality and relevance of the sources consulted; 5) Contributions to existing knowledge.

Once the article is refereed, the concept of publication will be made known through an email to the contact author (s). If adjustments to the article are required (Accepted after completing corrections), the author (s) will have a maximum period of 15 days to make the adjustments (this period is part of the 5 weeks of Phase 2), and they must send a new version of the document and a letter in which each one of the suggestions / observations issued by the evaluators is answered. It is the responsibility of the authors to comply with all the suggestions and recommendations sent; if there are disagreements, they should inform and argue their position. The editor decides if the modified article is sent again to the same peer evaluators assigned to request their final endorsement. Once the comments, concepts or corrections are received, the editor, together with the Editorial Committee, makes the final decision of Accepted for Publication or Not Accepted, as the case may be.

If the article is Accepted for publication (without corrections or minimal corrections) the authors must comply with the delivery of; a) the final version of the article in Spanish or English, according to the preference of the authors; (b) an authorization to the Editorial Committee of the journal for the reproduction of text with the authors' signatures; and (c) the identification data of the authors for the respective journal database (ORCID code, full names and email).

Rejected articles (Not accepted for publication) will be notified to their authors via email.

Stage 3: Once the article is accepted, the final editing and layout process begins, in three (3) weeks, which includes the assignment of DOI and publication of the material in electronic format on the Clío platform. Journal of History, Human Sciences and Critical Thought.